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**Paper Title: “The monopoly on reason as a manifestation of exclusive knowledge:
Speculation, libertarian enclaves, and the reproduction of difference through narratives
on the future.”**

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Abstract

The paper addresses how private city projects associated with “enclave libertarianism” (Lynch 2017) utilise discursive practices grounded in mobilising a monopoly on reason and rationality (Gordon 2021) to reproduce notions of social difference that justify capitalist exploitation (Bear 2020). Descriptions of the ultimate utility of sovereign libertarian enclaves promoted in corners of the Global South by “exit libertarians” (Craib 2022) from the Global North (e.g., Próspera ZEDE off the North coast of Honduras), stress access to expert and privileged knowledge that makes it possible to anticipate the development of volatile and uncertain markets in the future (i.e., “narrative authority”, Leins 2020) as well as modes of governance. In turn, local contestations to the expert knowledge mobilised by representatives of private city projects are countered as misinformed, tendentious, or even wilfully ignorant appreciations of experiments in free-market capitalism and governance. The success of private city projects becomes a process of mobilising exclusive knowledge of the future and disavowing all other potential claims to that knowledge. To develop my argument, I focus on the narratives offered by one private city representative (Próspera ZEDE) and competing claims offered by two representatives from a village adjacent to and affected by Próspera ZEDE.

Keywords: Speculation; dehumanization; reason; libertarian enclaves; Bay Islands, Honduras

Introduction

In this presentation, I address how Employment and Economic Development Zones in Honduras, or ZEDEs, are partly constituted through what Stefan Leins (2020) terms narrative authority. I note that ZEDEs' speculative practices construct visions of the future that dehumanize specific human groups and institutional projects by mobilizing appeals to a circumspect reason that both belies the racial privilege attached to speculators and which presents itself as expert knowledge of the future by appealing to factors not generally acknowledged as part of expert discourse. After brief descriptions of how I am employing dehumanization, speculation, and narrative authority, I point to how one Próspera ZEDE representative (Ernesto Zambrano, pseudonym) expanded on the speculative promise of ZEDEs during an interview.

So, what are ZEDEs? Andrea Nuila (Nuila 2022) refers to Employment and Economic Development zones, or ZEDEs, as special economic zones (SEZ) that “hold a significant degree of judicial, administrative, and legislative autonomy against the rest of the Honduran territory,” with a potentiated ability to organize social, economic, and political life without the involvement of the Honduran central government through private service providers. ZEDEs are associated with the Free Private City (Geglia and Nuila 2021) movement and fit within a long standing Euroamerican libertarian (Craib 2018) desire to establish new forms of governance in, primarily, non-Euroamerican countries. As others have already noted, ZEDEs employ legal mechanisms for land grabbing (Martin and Geglia 2019; Roux and Geglia 2019) reminiscent of colonial expansion, are supported by coalitions of Euroamerican transnational (Craib 2022) interests that vie against democratic rule, and are exercises in capitalist speculation mediated through symbolic violence and erasure (Martin and Geglia 2019). For some analysts, ZEDEs constitute the establishment of new countries within

Honduras and a loss of territorial sovereignty (García Rodríguez 2021). Others have compared ZEDEs to the monoculture enclaves that operated in Honduras at the beginning of the 20th century (Lynch 2019; Martin and Geglia 2019; Roux and Geglia 2019)—which enjoyed an extraordinary degree of autonomy (Ochoa 2015)—to stress the similarities between ZEDEs and recently experienced neocolonial mechanisms for extractive exploitation. Recently, Nuila (2022) described ZEDEs as special economic zones that most closely resembled Gebel’s (2020) Free Private Cities, meaning semi-autonomous jurisdictions with the capability to organize social, political, and economic life without the involvement of a central government and administered exclusively through private service providers. ZEDEs have an ability to operate almost completely independently of the central government through the CAMP (Committee on the Adoption of Best Practices) (Geglia 2016; García Rodríguez 2021) and can design and implement their own legal constitutions known as ‘charters,’ carry out their own land registries, and devise their own monetary policy, among other issues (Nuila 2022: 7). The law that allowed for the creation of ZEDEs was repealed early in 2022 but at least 2 ZEDEs continue operating on Honduran territory and earlier this year, one of these ZEDEs, Prospera ZEDE, attempted to begin an international arbitration process with the Honduran government.

Much of the public discourse that accompanied the implementation of Prospera ZEDE referred to the advantages of participating in a properly functioning free-market economy. In this case, a properly functioning market economy should be understood under the dictates of neoclassical economics as one in which a capitalist market organizes and intervenes upon every conceivable aspect of life. As such, Prospera ZEDE and other ZEDEs are presented as sand boxes or experimental arenas where free-market principles are allowed to operate freely and unencumbered by governmental regulation. Although usually presented as a matter of reasonable approaches to the organization of life or the sensible development of competitive

pressures on governance to create better governance products, ZEDE discourse contains a definite conviction that a free-market economy is a matter of natural law (Polanyi 2001). In this sense, allowing the free-market to take hold carries with it an inevitable success, always profiled against that which it is not or that which it is attempting to avoid on the way to said success, mainly, welfare-oriented bureaucratic governance thought to hamper the operation of the free-market.

In earlier work, Leins (2018) discussed how the success of financial analysts depended on their ability to construct compelling predictions regarding the futures of given financial markets. For Leins' (2018), financial analysts labored to produce coherent narratives about the future that other market actors could then use to make decisions regarding their involvement in each market. This entailed some calculative practices but relied to a significant extent on non-calculative approaches that could make the results of calculative practices come together in a way that hinted deeper insight into unacknowledged developments that could profoundly impact the marketplace. Through "narrative authority," Leins (2020) extends this insight to argue that while constructing the future of markets as certain or inherently knowable, economic experts maneuver around practices of speculation and valuation to mobilize their expertise in a manner that is persuasive to a given target audience and which corresponds to their own held convictions or "feelings" of the future of given markets (Leins 2020: 7-8). An important feature of Leins' (2020) argument, drawn from Laura Bear's (Bear 2020a) theorizations on speculation, is that economic experts succeed at profiling themselves as experts with intimate foresight to the extent that they can navigate uncertainty by producing convincing images of the future using "affect, calculative approaches, tacit knowledge and embodied experience" (Leins 2020: 4). "Narrative authority" (Leins 2020) then is an actor's ability to convince others about their own deeply held assumptions and constructions of the future by mobilizing many elements not assumed

to be part of expert discourse, but which none-the-less are indispensable to the construction of tangible images of that very same future.

Operationalizing speculation, dehumanization, and reason

Here it is necessary to address how Laura Bear (Bear 2020a, 2020b, 2015) and Lewis Gordon (Gordon 1995, 2015, 2011, 2021) theorize speculation and dehumanization, respectively, in order to delve into additional attributes of narrative authority not yet considered within Leins' theorization. Bear invites us to complicate our understanding of speculation by moving beyond the purely economic onto addressing how speculation, as a future-oriented social activity, rests on two aspirational pillars. One pillar is the accumulation of capital in the future, and the other is the re/creation of desired socio-racial hierarchies that enable the exploitation that leads to capital accumulation. For Bear (2020b), the accumulation of value in the future depends on constructing *social differences* (e.g., racial, national, social) in the present that can be manufactured as sources of uncertainty to accumulation, while presenting these differences as obstacles that are maneuverable by speculators in the near future. This means that anticipating the future of capital leads to manufacturing expectations for the degree of involvement of a given *race* or *nation* in that same future, as well as explanations for current sociopolitical dynamics, in a way that privileges and justifies certain stable long-term linkages over others.

Here, I understand the creation of social difference and the role of reason in the continuation of social difference through the work of philosopher Lewis Gordon. Gordon makes a distinction between reason and rationality (Gordon 2011; 2021). Reason is an open, ongoing, and incomplete relationship to reality. To practice reason, one must recognize that reality is vast and because of this vastness contradictions to our organized modes of thought are virtually inevitable. Rationality, on the other hand, is about absolute consistency.

Rationality provides the foundation for scientific practice through the establishment of expected models for behavior and in some cases for the establishment of presumed natural laws. Rationality relates to an unwavering certainty regarding expected behaviors and outcomes, which Gordon (2011) concedes works well with so-called hard or exact sciences but is not such a useful tool for the human sciences. As is to be expected, problems arise in the form of contradictions when established models of behavior are unable to account for variation or deviation from actually existing reality. If to deal with these contradictions disciplines, or practices of knowledge production and communication, turn in on themselves for justification, this leads to what Gordon terms 'disciplinary decadence' (2011), or situations where organized ways of thinking are given primacy over reality to maintain the internal consistency and legitimacy of said system of organized thought. Under a situation of 'disciplinary decadence,' adherents of certain practices or institutions expect reality to adhere to accepted conventions, as opposed to reformulating or reconsidering convention to account for reality. Such a practice entails an abandonment of reason in favor of rationality (Gordon 2011). This leads to preserving the consistency of the system over acknowledging reality, which in turn leads to hoarded reason or distorted reason (Gordon 2021): reason that is thought to be able to stand on its own, apart from reality, as complete and unaccountable to the external world. So, disciplinary decadence arises when a given system of organized thought is believed to be complete and absolute and therefore God-like (Gordon 2021), in the process abandoning a relationship to reality in an attempt to become reality itself. This leads to two relevant insights for this presentation. First, for the system to remain consistent despite reality, everything that contradicts the system must be placed outside of the system. That means that even though a given phenomenon may have been produced by the system, it is thought to be external to and completely independent from the system itself. For example, under neoclassical capitalism any failures of the market as evidenced in soaring

unemployment, inflation, exploitation, necro-capitalism, environmental degradation through unbridled extractive industries, or over accumulation, to name a few, are usually related to not having enough of a free-market economy and overly stringent regulation (Gordon 2021). Second, preserving the absoluteness and completeness of a given system in a social world means accounting for how different groups of people fare under a system assumed to be natural. To this effect, entire groups of people are also placed outside of the system to preserve the notion that the system is absolute or, in this case, just (Gordon 2011). In other words, other human beings negatively impacted by the functioning of the system under a Euromodern world order, usually non-European racialized populations, are turned into non-Others and placed in the zone of non-being (Gordon 2015), or what we should understand following Gordon, as a dominant practice under colonialism: “the furious determination to deny an Other all attributes of humanity” (Gordon 1995). Denying an Other attributes of humanity requires that one lie to oneself about the reality of an Other (or group of Others) and, in the process, suspend the possibility of forming an ethical relationship (Gordon 2015) between individuals as human beings. With the suspension of an ethical relationship, there are no limits to what an individual in a dominant position can subject on another since this other is not acknowledged as a human Other. Re/creating social difference turns into the delimitation of groups between which an ethical relationship will not be sustained. In this way, re/creating social difference turns into a mechanism for justifying the processes employed to extract value under capitalism (e.g., exploitation), since individuals located outside of an ethical relationship (i.e., outside of humanity) do not belong in the future (Gordon 2021) but rather exist to make the future possible for others acknowledged as *human*. In short, to reason requires being open to the perspective of another Other as a legitimate vantage point on social reality (Gordon 2011; 2021), for which it is necessary to recognize another Other as a human Other.

To that effect, “narrative authority” could also be understood as a practice that draws on racialized privilege as an additional element not assumed to be part of expert discourse, which takes advantage of imagined “social differences” between differentially positioned social actors. “Narrative authority” could also entail the ability to convince others of a particular version of the future that depends on ignoring reality as it currently is (by ignoring alternate perspectives and vantage points, along with other possible futures) to satisfy a particular idea of the present and a desire for what the future should be. “Narrative authority” may conceal a commitment to specific futures in which groups of people placed outside of the system do not figure as meaningful participants but rather are constructed as anomalous features of the present and obstacles to the future.

Próspera according to EZ: On the necessity and desirability of foreign control

Mr. Zambrano saw the ZEDE law as an opportunity to implement change through radical reforms in a way that was not possible following established administrative, legal, or political mechanisms. “I’m a political reformer,” he said at one point, “I want what’s best for Honduras. I’m working because I genuinely believe ZEDEs, autonomy, and decentralization *is the way to go.*” Sometime later he followed with, “For me it’s like, *let’s take the easy way out, OK?* This is easier...It’s not ideal, it’s not perfect, but it’s better than what we have. It might not meet some theoretical ideal” but “it’s easier and it’s better and it lets me bring investment.” For Mr. Zambrano, any worthwhile reform in Honduras needed to attract foreign investment. The general idea being foreign investment would generate local wealth, which would generate employment and eventually generalized prosperity. Eventual generalized prosperity loomed large to both justify the conditions under which the ZEDE law was passed and to discredit any past and present opposition to the project. In addressing the conceptual genesis of the ZEDE law in 2010, Mr. Zambrano commented: “the thing is there

was a destitution and forced expatriation [of the sitting president in 2009] and there was a crisis for six months...There's chaos! ... If this happened now, what's going to happen later? ... the creation of these autonomous regimes was conceived, so that they could be insulated from the crisis and political disaster." At the same time, he viewed the conditions under which the ZEDE regime was finally approved in 2013, after the Supreme Court (Geglia 2016) was unconstitutionally replaced, as coincidental and related solely to a pre-existing electoral law dispute within the governing party at the time. Mr. Zambrano considered that the lawyers that presented an unconstitutionality claim on the ZEDE law to the newly appointed Supreme Court had simply decided to place their trust in the continued functioning of a government body: "Boom! They give the court a coup. What should I do? Should I wait 10 years for a [good] government to come along?" Mr. Zambrano made sure to remind me that the ZEDE law was approved by the national congress through a sanctioned voting procedure conducted by elected representatives.

Mr. Zambrano's discourse was animated by the persistent undercurrent that Honduran institutions had failed and that achieving a desirable future required the involvement of outside actors. This leads to at least two interrelated observations. Mr. Zambrano alluded to the Honduran government as irredeemably unstable and granted Honduran institutions a fixity that belied the possibility for change. Considering institutions (Abellán 2014) are the product of social relations oriented towards the social re/production of the world, this inability to change becomes a reference to the people who could be expected to occupy Honduran institutions: other Hondurans. This leads to positing that corruption was intrinsic to *Honduranness*, crafting Hondurans in and of themselves as obstacles in the way of prosperity. The second observation is that foreign control is better by virtue of not being Honduran control. However, the bevy of SEZs that have invited foreign control over domestic production, and which have operated across Honduras for the last 20 years, have not

led to a generalized prosperity. Local analysts like Marlon Ochoa (2015) have already demonstrated SEZs in Honduras have led to a general loss of tax revenue for local municipalities, the precarization of wage labour, and to an increase in local violence.

Próspera according to EZ: On Honduran governance as inimical to freedom

Mr. Zambrano's reservations on the actual existence of democratic governance and political participation within Honduras only served to accentuate an immediate need for ZEDEs. Mr. Zambrano noted, "the counter proposal is this: ZEDEs would be legitimate if authorized by a constitutional and democratic government...if that's the standard...well, then, I would say, maybe we wouldn't need [ZEDEs]." This line of thought fed back into the idea that Honduran democratic governance had never been legitimate. Mr. Zambrano stressed to me, "If you have more than 60 percent of your population in poverty, incredibly high violence indices, high corruption, lack of independence between state powers, we are not talking about a civil and democratic government." For Mr. Zambrano, the Honduran government had simply failed along with any local extension of the Honduran government. There was little that a new government could offer in the future to regain its legitimacy in the present short of "Honduras copying the best practices we have [at Próspera]." However, Próspera was legitimate now based on what it could do in the future, such as the more than "one thousand million dollars of direct foreign investment" in the next 50 years that will "generate competitive incentives" and a "better governance product" as ZEDEs become more widely adopted. The legitimacy of ZEDEs was, at once, to be determined and already obtained: "...even if [ZEDEs] were borne from that structure... [ZEDEs are] going to allow me to change it. So, I think that adds a lot to the issue of legitimacy."

Próspera ZEDE's promise of prosperity required a separation from the Honduran government. Próspera ZEDE needed to exist outside of the Honduran government because

Honduran governance appeared illegitimate on one count and spurious on another. First, it was illegitimate because it represented the failure of democratic governance. Second, it was spurious because it could only aspire to become democratic by adopting foreign models. Simply, the Honduran government could not deliver on either democracy or prosperity. Próspera's creation did not just entail separating Próspera from Honduran administration but locating the entirety of Honduran governance outside of a system seen as conducive to the creation of prosperity. In turn, achieving a desired future required limiting the participation (and protection) of Hondurans within the construction of the future or very strictly organizing the way Hondurans could expect to participate in the future: as non-Hondurans or individuals stripped of protections under Honduran law. Accepting ZEDEs seemed to require identifying Honduran governance as in the way of progress and wealth creation, over recognizing that the current social, economic, and political realities that affect Honduras are in great measure the result of geopolitical machinations that have favored foreign capital to the detriment of local socioeconomic conditions, as Marvin Barahona (Barahona 2018) and Adrienne Pine (Pine 2008) have separately argued.

Speculation as the path to (the *rationality* of) colonial capitalism

As speculators, ZEDE promoters imagine and navigate a desired future social reality by constructing Honduran governance and Honduran citizenship as maneuverable obstacles in the way of future capital accumulation. Ultimately, Honduran governance and Honduran citizenship were constructed as in the way of *the* valued future. During the interview, Mr. Zambrano constructed both Honduran governance and Hondurans as obstacles to wealth creation and articulated how the speculative promise contained in Próspera ZEDE depended on mitigating both. In Mr. Zambrano's estimation, there was only one legitimate type of growth and productivity that could be pursued by the Honduran government, which basically

amounted to abandoning Honduran governance. Bear (2015) already observed that under capitalism labor is differentially valued according to the individual performing the labor. As a case in point, the potential labor performed by ZEDE speculators was regarded as productive labor, whereas the potential labor performed by Hondurans and the Honduran government was regarded as destructive labor. The difference between the two is not a function of the type of labor under consideration but a function of the value ascribed to the individual or individuals laboring. Mr. Zambrano' ability to present Próspera ZEDE as the mechanism for achieving the desired future rested on the conviction that free-market principles encapsulated in Próspera ZEDE were the only way of achieving prosperity, but also the only way of ensuring Honduran governance and Honduran involvement was limited in the creation of the very same future, so as not to encumber the desired future. In portraying Honduran governance as an obstacle and Próspera ZEDE as a necessary institutional response, Mr. Zambrano had to conceive of capitalist free-market principles as absolute and self-evident and any opposition had to be placed outside of the system represented by Próspera ZEDE. In that sense, any failure would turn into a failure borne from failing to fully adopt Próspera ZEDE's institutional design, with its ever-expanding requirements, or failure borne from not belonging to those population groups for whom the future was guaranteed.

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